

Created Artifact	Explanation	Examples
Processed Data	Data that has been processed in some for, e.g., cleaned of errors or changed file format	
Data Quality Ratings	Ratings of data quality	
Metadata	Added metadata like time of creation or publisher	
Feedback/Experience reports	Reports about usage of data outlining issues encountered, potentially communicated to the publisher as feedback	
Documentation	Documentation about how to use the data, either for the user themselves or to share	
Source Code	Programms or scripts to automate activities	
Notebooks	Sourcecode, documentation and execution bundles like Jupyter Notebooks	Jupyter
CI definitions	Continuous integration setups	
Comments on data	Comments on data	